
Between Practice and Preference: Students and Society in Learning English Through I Can Speak Program

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ABSTRACT: This research investigates the usage behavior of the "I Can Speak" program on Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo, Indonesia as a medium for learning English, differences in preferences between students and the general public. Utilizing qualitative research methods with a case study approach, data were collected through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions (FGD), and program observations. The findings reveal that students favor practical broadcasting experiences to meet academic requirements and improve their speaking skills, finding the role of a radio broadcaster more appealing than merely listening to the radio, which they perceive as outdated. Conversely, the general public exhibits a strong interest in listening to the program but is reluctant to engage actively due to social stigma that views English as a pretentious language. This research underscores the necessity of creating a supportive developing programs that not only enhance language proficiency but also build listeners' confidence. Proposed strategies to boost engagement include increasing interactive elements in the program, conducting awareness campaigns about the benefits of learning English, and providing training in a non-threatening environment. By connecting content to local culture, Radio Pesona FM creates a more inclusive atmosphere for learning English, encouraging greater participation and increasing listener confidence. as an evaluation and inspiration for other broadcast media in the Wonosobo local area in creating educational programs that invite the community to learn English, through radio media but with packaging that is adapted to the customs and identity of the local community.

KEYWORDS: English Learning, Radio Media, Listener Involvement, Education, FGD

I. INTRODUCTION

English is an international language that is very important in global communication (Mamadjanova and Malikova, 2023). In Indonesia, proficiency in English is becoming increasingly crucial given its role in various aspects of life, including education, business, and technology (Febriana et al., 2024). For that reason, effective and engaging learning methods are essential to improve the English language skills of the community, especially in areas that are less accessible to formal education (Annamalai, Uthayakumaran and Zyoud, 2023).

Radio media, as one form of mass media, has great potential in conveying information and education to the wider community (Aondowase, Udoudom and Pam, 2023). The advantage of radio lies in its ability to reach listeners in various locations without requiring internet access or advanced devices (Ojwang, 2023). This makes radio an ideal tool for introducing and teaching English to communities that may not have the opportunity to learn formally (Herfandi and Wahyudi, 2023). I Can Speak program in Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo, Indonesia can serve as a concrete example of utilizing radio media in English language learning. With programs specifically designed to improve listeners' English language skills, this radio can present interactive and engaging content. For example, programs that involve dialogues in English, quizzes, or discussions about English-speaking cultures can help listeners learn in an enjoyable way.

One of the advantages of using radio as a learning medium is its flexibility (Sofi-Karim, Bali and Rached, 2023). Listeners can learn anytime and anywhere, whether while driving, working, or doing other daily activities (Havrylenko, 2023). This provides an opportunity for individuals with limited time to still access English learning materials. In addition, radio can also create a familiar atmosphere between the broadcaster and the listeners (Vailati and Lima, 2023; Reková, 2024). With an informal and communicative approach, listeners will feel more comfortable and open to learning (Jufri et al., 2023). This is very important in the language learning process, where confidence in speaking and listening is the key to success (Costigan and Brink, 2020).

The use of audio media such as radio has also proven effective in improving English language proficiency (Ezeh, Anidi and Nwokolo, 2021). Audio media can help students better understand pronunciation and vocabulary (Harsa, Saragih and Husein, 2020). By listening to conversations in English directly from native speakers through the radio, listeners can learn in a more

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natural way (Djabborova, 2020). In the context of Wonosobo, the use of I Can Speak program in Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo Indonesia as a medium for learning English can also contribute to the development of the local community. By providing relevant educational programs, this radio not only enhances the community's English language skills but also strengthens the sense of togetherness and local identity through content that aligns with the local culture (Achmad et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the use of radio media in English language learning aligns with the trend of educational globalization that increasingly emphasizes the use of technology and digital media (Frolova, Rogach and Ryabova, 2020; Matthew et al., 2022). Although radio is not a new technology, its role in education remains relevant and important to optimize in facing the challenges of the times (Haleem et al., 2022). Overall, the use of Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo as a medium for learning English offers many benefits to the local community. With a creative and innovative approach, it is hoped that these programs can improve the listeners' English language skills and open up broader opportunities for them to communicate at an international level (Aziiz and Shabana, 2023). In this context, the Interactive Radio Instruction (IRI) theory emerges as an innovative solution that can address these challenges (Elliott and Lashley, 2017).

Interactive Radio Instruction (IRI) is a teaching style in which a radio broadcast accompanies a teacher and learners through the actions of a lesson (Damani and Mitchell, 2020). The IRI theory emphasizes the use of radio media as an interactive teaching tool capable of reaching students in remote areas, where access to formal education may be limited. Through this approach, students not only listen to the learning material but are also encouraged to actively participate, answer questions, and engage in discussions. Thus, IRI not only improves students' English skills but also encourages social interaction and collaboration among students. This approach is highly relevant in the context of the research "Between Practice and Preference: Students and Society in Learning English through the I Can Speak Program" in Wonosobo, Indonesia which aims to explore how students and society interact with the IRI-based English learning program.

This research examines the concept of Interactive Radio Instruction (IRI) specifically designed for English language learning (Yaumi, 2021). Unlike traditional broadcasts, IRI actively involves listeners during lessons, thereby encouraging better engagement and retention of language skills (Bangsawan, 2024). This research also proposes the development of local radio content that reflects the cultural and social context of the community in Wonosobo. This initiative aims to create a more meaningful connection between the community and learning materials, enhancing motivation and relevance in language learning.

Furthermore, by integrating sound effects, music, and interactive elements into the radio program, this research aims to create a multimodal learning environment that caters to various learning styles. This approach is expected to make language acquisition more dynamic and enjoyable for the community. This research also emphasizes the importance of specialized training programs for radio broadcasters on how to effectively use radio as an educational tool. This initiative aims to empower educators with the skills necessary to successfully integrate radio into their teaching practices.

Previous research has discussed the importance of using radio as a tool for learning English, but there are still some gaps that have not been addressed. One of them is the lack of focus on the potential of local radio in the context of language education. I Can Speak program in Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo, as a local radio station, has great potential to improve the English language skills of the community in the area, but there has not been much in-depth research on how this local radio station can contribute to the language learning process. Therefore, this research aims to utilize radio media, specifically I Can Speak program in Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo, as an interactive and effective tool for English language learning.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Importance of English in Global Communication

English has evolved into the primary international language that dominates cross-border communication, serving as a lingua franca in various contexts, from business meetings to international academic events (Mamadjanova and Malikova, 2023). Along with globalization, the demand for English proficiency has increased rapidly, considering its function of uniting individuals from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds (Mohammed and Abdalla, 2020; Salih and Omar, 2021). This language is now considered an important asset in enhancing the competitiveness of individuals and nations, opening access to global educational resources, cutting-edge research, and extensive business and professional networks (Wieczorek, Mitreĝa and Spáčil, 2021).

Many multinational and local companies require English proficiency for candidates who want to advance in strategic positions, so English language skills directly impact better career opportunities and higher salaries (Aondowase, Udoudom and Pam, 2023). Mastery of this language also enables individuals to access scientific literature, new technologies, and modern learning methods, most of which are presented in English (Bin-Hady and Al-Tamimi, 2021).

B. Effective Learning Methods

In an effort to improve the English language skills of the community, especially in areas that are difficult to reach with formal education, interactive and engaging learning methods are highly necessary. (Annamalai, Uthayakumaran and Zyoud, 2023) emphasize that approaches involving active participation can motivate participants to be more engaged and practice more. This method helps overcome the boredom that often arises from conventional learning, thereby increasing interest and motivation to

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learn (Amril and Suarni, 2023). With this approach, communities in areas with limited access to formal education still have the opportunity to learn English effectively.

Radio has become one of the most potential media in supporting this effort due to its ability to reach listeners in various locations, including remote areas (Sanusi et al., 2021). As stated by (Ojwang, 2023), radio has the advantage of conveying information without requiring internet access or sophisticated electronic devices, which can be difficult to obtain in rural areas. In the current digital era, the presence of radio as a medium for learning foreign languages might be considered outdated, but in reality, it is still very relevant for communities with limited access to technology (Rikitianskaia and Balbi, 2020). Radio enables the dissemination of English language learning without the accessibility barriers often encountered in online media (Nkengbeza, Mbuji and Chainda, 2022).

A radio program designed with educational and interactive content can change the perception of learning English to be more enjoyable (Gracella and Nur, 2020). For example, programs that present dialogues in English, quizzes about culture, and examples of everyday conversations in contexts familiar to the local community. (Herfandi and Wahyudi, 2023) note that an approach that combines entertainment and education can make learning more effective because it reduces anxiety in learning a foreign language. Listeners are invited to participate, for example through phone calls or text messages, in language quizzes or conversations, which not only improve their skills but also make the learning process more engaging (Terzioğlu and Kurt, 2022).

C. Effectiveness of Audio Media

The use of audio media such as radio has proven to be very effective in supporting English language learning, especially in enhancing listening skills and understanding conversation contexts (Yurko and Styfanyshyn, 2020). Through radio media, listeners can learn the pronunciation of words and expressions used in everyday conversations, making them more familiar with the intonation and rhythm of English (Zulfikar, Aulia and Akmal, 2020). Research by (Harsa, Saragih and Husein, 2020; Ezeh, Anidi and Nwokolo, 2021) shows that listening directly to native speakers, or simulating conversations with a natural speaking style, can help listeners understand more complex vocabulary and language structures. In the long term, exposure to English through radio can improve language skills without the need to attend formal classes, which are often difficult for people in remote areas to access.

In Wonosobo, Radio Pesona FM serves as a real example of how radio media is utilized as a tool for learning English that reaches many people. Through creatively packaged programs, listeners not only receive training in English but also content tailored to the local culture. (Achmad et al., 2021) emphasize that the language learning program at Radio Pesona FM has successfully introduced English in a local context, for example, through everyday dialogues relevant to the lives of the Wonosobo community. This is important because it helps listeners learn English without feeling that their culture is being sidelined, making the learning process more easily accepted and appreciated by the audience (Benattabou, 2020). In this way, language learning on the radio not only provides new knowledge but also encourages listeners to feel proud of their culture (Gereda, 2020). This effort creates a bridge between globalization and the preservation of local identity, which ultimately can build a society that is broad-minded without forgetting its cultural roots.

D. Globalization of Education and Radio

The use of radio media in the context of educational globalization is becoming increasingly relevant as the use of technology and digital media expands in various aspects of life (Osuji and Amadi, 2020). This trend is evident in efforts to utilize digital platforms to expand access to information and learning in society (Frolova, Rogach and Ryabova, 2020; Matthew et al., 2022). Although it has been around for quite some time, radio technology continues to demonstrate its role in effectively reaching a wide audience, including in areas that may have limited access to the internet or other digital devices. Considering its great potential, the use of radio in education is very important to continue optimizing, especially as a medium that is friendly to various groups, from students to the general public (Haleem et al., 2022).

In this digital era, the use of radio as an educational medium opens up great opportunities for the community to develop relevant skills, one of which is English language proficiency (Sinha, 2022). With a creative approach, broadcast programs focused on English language training can provide listeners with a space to learn in a more relaxed atmosphere, free from the burdens of a formal classroom setting (Asmani, 2018). Radio can provide interactive language learning, for example through programs that involve listeners to participate actively, thus creating a more engaging learning experience (Zhao and Lai, 2023). With innovative presentations, radio has great potential to help improve listeners' English skills, both directly and indirectly (Aziiz and Shabana, 2023).

Through the development of educational programs, such as radio broadcasts that provide special segments for language learning, it is hoped that the community can access English language learning more easily and affordably (Prahmana et al., 2021). This step is also in line with the vision of creating a more competent society in facing the challenges of globalization, which increasingly demands proficiency in foreign languages. Radio is not just a medium of entertainment, but also a means of empowerment that can significantly enhance the skills of the community (Gangwani, Alruwaili and Safar, 2021). With the various

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programs specifically designed to improve English language skills, it is hoped that the contribution of radio to education can have a broader impact on society (Aliyah and Masyithoh, 2024).

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research method with a case study approach, focusing on the use of Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo as a medium for learning English. Data collection will be conducted through Focus Group Discussions (FGD), observations, and in-depth interviews with 12 informants, including:

- a) Loyal Listeners of Radio Pesona: Individuals who have been listening to Radio Pesona for more than three years.
- b) Occasional Listeners: Those who listen to the radio sporadically.
- c) Listeners with English Backgrounds: Participants who have previously studied or are currently learning and applying English.
- d) Listeners without English Backgrounds: Individuals who have no prior exposure to the English language.
- e) Radio Managers Directly Involved with Programs: Personnel who are directly responsible for the content and execution of educational programs.
- f) Radio Managers Not Directly Involved with Programs: Those who oversee the radio station but are not directly engaged in program content.
- g) Listeners Aged 20-30 Years: A demographic group that may have different learning needs and preferences.
- h) Listeners Aged 30+ Years: An older demographic that may approach language learning differently.
- i) Participants Involved in the "I Can Speak" Broadcast: Individuals who are directly engaged with this specific program aimed at enhancing English language skills.

Data collection was carried out through FGD, observation, and in-depth interviews with listeners, broadcasters, and radio managers, as well as observations of the programs broadcast (Sugiyono, 2018). Focus Group Discussion (FGD) can be examined through interviews with informants to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the obtained information. These interviews aim to clarify and delve into the perspectives of FGD participants or individuals who have a deep understanding of the discussed topic. By using appropriate interview methodologies, such as semi-structured interviews, researchers can explore information in greater depth. The data collected is then analyzed to identify themes and patterns, and compared with other data sources to ensure consistency. Through this process, the validity of the FGD data can be strengthened, providing a more comprehensive and valid picture of the issue being studied. In addition, analysis of the content of radio broadcasts will also be carried out to assess the relevance and effectiveness of the learning materials presented. With this approach, it is hoped that a deep understanding can be obtained regarding how radio can function as an interactive and effective learning tool in a local context (Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2014).

The theory underlying this research is Interactive Radio Instruction (IRI), which emphasizes the importance of active listener engagement in the learning process. IRI is different from traditional broadcasting because it encourages listener participation during lessons, thereby enhancing language skill retention. Additionally, the multimodal learning theory is also relevant, considering that this research will integrate various audio elements such as music and sound effects to create a dynamic and enjoyable learning environment. By adopting both of these theories, this research aims to explore the potential of radio in improving English language skills in the Wonosobo community.

In the implementation of research, it is important to involve the local community, colleges, and local society in the development of radio content that aligns with their culture and needs. This participatory approach not only enhances learning motivation but also ensures that the learning material is relevant and engaging for the audience. Training programs for radio broadcasters will also be a focus, so they can use radio effectively as an educational tool. Thus, this research is expected to make a significant contribution to the development of innovative English language learning methods through radio media.

IV. RESULT

This research found that there are two different behavior patterns between students and the general public in using I Can Speak program in Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo as a medium for learning English.

Item	College Student	Listener
Duration of listening	< 1 hours/days	> 2 hours/days
I Can Speak listening frequency	Approximately Once a Month	Approximately 2-4 Times per Month
Speaking Activity in the Program	At Least Once a Month (Based on the Broadcast and Attendance Schedule)	< 1 a Month (Based on the Results of the Observation)

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A. Student Preferences

This research shows a clear preference among students for practical broadcasting experiences compared to passive listening and participation in English programs. These preferences are influenced by several factors:

a) Motivation to Fulfill Academic Tasks:

1. Many students are willing and enthusiastic about doing radio broadcasts because it is a program from the campus to fulfill their academic assignments. Where direct radio broadcasting can train their English speaking skills.
2. Students are interested in becoming broadcasters not only from an academic perspective in fulfilling their assignments but also due to current trends such as podcasting. Students can express themselves through a radio broadcast model that appears relaxed and flexible in speaking English.

b) Limited Engagement in Listening: Students show a lack of interest in listening to English programs, which they find less engaging compared to direct experience in broadcasts. This is felt by students that listening to the radio seems outdated and uninteresting. Moreover, students find listening to radio broadcasts boring and not trendy in the current era.

c) Preference for Active Participation: Students prefer activities that allow them to participate actively, such as creating content or broadcasting, rather than being passive listeners. This is in line with educational theory that emphasizes that active learning is a more effective method for language acquisition.

Most of the students involved in this research showed a stronger preference for broadcasting practice rather than participating as program listeners. Students feel that the broadcasting experience provides them with the opportunity to practice and develop their speaking skills directly, especially public speaking through radio broadcasting, although they do not show the same interest in listening to programs or actively participating via phone. Moreover, being a guest host in an English learning program is considered interesting and cool, especially in this era where the digital world, particularly podcasts, is booming with light yet meaningful and positive content.

B. Response of the General Public

The social context in Wonosobo plays an important role in shaping the attitudes of students and the general public towards learning English:

- a) Cultural Stigma: Many individuals in Wonosobo are reluctant to use English because they fear being considered "pretentious." This stigma creates psychological barriers that prevent people from practicing their English skills, even though they have an interest in learning.
- b) Interest in Listening: Despite the stigma, there is significant interest among the community in listening to I Can Speak programs broadcasted by Radio Pesona FM. The community enjoys the content being aired, but often feels hesitant to participate actively due to concerns about peer judgment.

On the other hand, the people of Wonosobo show a high interest in listening to the I Can Speak programs broadcast by Radio Pesona FM. However, they tend to feel shy and hesitant to participate, whether as active listeners or in direct interactions such as making phone calls.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that although I Can Speak program in Radio Pesona FM has great potential as a tool for learning English, there are significant challenges in motivating both groups to engage more actively.

1. Students and Learning Media

Students who prefer radio broadcasting practice in the I Can Speak program reflect their needs and desires to meet academic demands and improve their English speaking skills. This shows that overly structured and task-based learning approaches can reduce their intrinsic motivation. Therefore, it is important to create a more engaging and relevant learning environment, where students not only feel pressured to complete tasks but also find value in the learning process itself.

Students are able to explore themselves in speaking English through the I Can Speak program on Pesona FM radio. Indirectly, this aligns with the opinion of (Aziiz and Shabana, 2023) which states that programs with creative and innovative approaches can develop good English speaking skills. Furthermore, this is an opportunity and a means of delivering interactive learning methods, where students can directly experience new experiences and a unique and engaging form of English speaking learning, which, in turn, develops very good and efficient speaking skills. This research aligns with the multimodal learning model, which refers to an approach that integrates various methods and channels in the learning process, including visual, auditory, and kinesthetic (Firmansyah and Suchaina, 2023). In the context of this research, students' preference for practical broadcast experiences reflects a multimodal approach.

2. Social Barriers in Society

The discomfort of the Wonosobo community in using English can be linked to the social stigma of "pretending to be English." Previous research shows that social support and a supportive environment are very important in the language learning process (Costigan and Brink, 2020). In fact, the community frequently enjoys the I Can Speak program. Therefore, Radio Pesona FM

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needs to develop a program that not only focuses on language learning but also builds the listeners' confidence. This research is supported by engagement theory, which focuses on the importance of active participation in the learning process (Miliszewska and Horwood, 2006). In this study, students showed a strong preference for actively participating in broadcasts rather than just listening.

The social stigma associated with the use of English in the Wonosobo community can hinder the language learning process, as individuals feel uncomfortable and fear being perceived as "show off" if they use the language. This reduces motivation and active participation in learning, creating a negative cycle where the lack of English usage leads to a lack of skills. To address this issue, programs like I Can Speak need to create a safe and supportive environment where participants can practice without fear of being judged. By integrating participatory elements and respecting local identities, Radio Pesona FM can act as an agent of change, making English language learning a positive and empowering experience for the community.

3. Strategy to Increase Participation

To address this challenge, several appropriate strategies that can be implemented are as follows:

- a) **Interactive Program:** Enhancing the interactive elements in the I Can Speak program on Pesona FM radio, such as quizzes or Q&A sessions involving listeners, which have actually been implemented, but there hasn't been much enthusiasm from the community or students in participating in these activities. This might be due to the infrequency of Q&A sessions during the program, which makes listeners less aware. The need for more complex socialization and collaboration, as well as a refresh of the I Can Speak program concept, is necessary so that students are also willing to listen and participate in the Q&A sessions.
- b) **Awareness Campaign:** Conduct a campaign that educates the public about the benefits of learning English and reduces existing stigma. Collaborating with community leaders or local influencers to talk about the importance of English can help change negative perceptions.
- c) **Training and Mentoring:** Providing training for the community who want to learn English, with a non-intimidating approach, and offering support from experienced tutors.

The theory of social stigma explains how social norms and values can influence individual behavior (Heatherton, 2003). In the context of Wonosobo society, the stigma against the use of English creates psychological barriers for individuals to practice English.

4. The Role of Radio in Building Local Identity

Radio Pesona FM can also focus on developing content that reflects local culture, so that listeners feel more connected to the material being studied. By linking English with local contexts, the community may feel more motivated to learn and use the language without fear of judgment.

This research highlights a significant gap between students' preferences for broadcasting practice and social perceptions that hinder broader participation in English programs in Wonosobo. By addressing these challenges through innovative program design and community engagement, it is hoped that a more supportive environment for English language learning can be created, encouraging both students and the general public to participate actively and confidently. This indirectly states that students' perception of listening to radio as being out of trend is incorrect, because by listening to the I Can Speak radio program, students can develop English learning materials where each broadcaster has different topics and each broadcaster's presentation style, which may improve and evolve. So that on the next occasion, the guest announcer can create a more complex and interesting script, and in terms of delivery, they can already do it more maturely. Social learning theory emphasizes the importance of observation and social interaction in the learning process (Bandura, 1989). In this context, although the Wonosobo community is interested in listening to the I Can Speak program, they feel hesitant to participate due to fear of judgment from others.

In conclusion, although I Can Speak program on Radio Pesona FM Wonosobo has great potential as a tool for learning English, further efforts are needed to increase community and student engagement. With a more inclusive and supportive approach, it is hoped that social barriers can be reduced and confidence in using English among listeners can be increased.

VI. CONCLUSION

The research investigated the differing behavior patterns of students and the general public in Wonosobo regarding their use of I Can Speak program on Radio Pesona FM as a medium for learning English. It revealed that students exhibit a clear preference for practical broadcasting experiences rather than passive listening. This preference is influenced by their motivation to fulfill academic tasks and their desire for active participation in English programs. Many students find direct engagement in radio broadcasting to be a valuable opportunity to improve their speaking skills, especially in a contemporary context where trends like podcasting are popular.

Conversely, the general public in Wonosobo demonstrates a reluctance to use English due to cultural stigma, fearing they may be perceived as "pretentious." Despite this apprehension, there is a notable interest in listening to the I Can Speak programs aired by Radio Pesona FM. However, many community members feel shy and hesitant to participate actively, whether through phone

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interactions or other means. This social barrier highlights the need for a supportive environment that encourages language learning without fear of judgment.

To enhance engagement among both students and the community, the research suggests implementing several strategies. These include enhancing interactive elements in the I Can Speak program, conducting awareness campaigns to educate the public about the benefits of learning English, and providing training and mentoring in a non-intimidating manner. By addressing these challenges and creating content that resonates with local culture, Radio Pesona FM can foster a more inclusive atmosphere for English language learning, ultimately encouraging greater participation and confidence in using English among listeners.

It is recommended that future researchers explore the use of other media, such as digital platforms and mobile applications, which can complement the radio program in improving English language skills. In addition, longitudinal studies examining the long-term impact of the I Can Speak program on participants' English language skills are also highly necessary. Such research can provide deeper insights into the effectiveness of various language learning methods, as well as how greater involvement in these programs can change societal attitudes towards the use of English. Thus, the results of this research will not only be beneficial for the development of radio programs but can also make a significant contribution to broader language teaching strategies in society.

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